

WEAVING

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Annotation: In this article discusses about weaving and given some important informations about it

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In the Surkhan oasis, weaving was considered one of the developed branches of handicraft. Despite the peculiar development of weaving in other territories, it was this industry that was strongly developed in Baysun and Denau. By weaving at home, silk and semi-silk were made. Especially a lot of materials were woven such as motley (striped cotton fabric), alacha (a kind of striped cotton or semi-silk fabric of handicraft production), thin fabric with colored stripes, chintz, ganda, silk, satin, calico (coarse cotton fabric), snipe (grade silk fabric). varieties of In addition, outerwear and fabrics such as shol, basma, kokma (woolen fabric) were mainly prepared from wool. Weaving also included yarn spinning, silk production and dyeing.

The main raw materials of spinners were cotton, wool and silk. Fabrics produced in this area were distinguished by color and beauty. The production of materials and fabrics was associated with the traditional economic activities of the population.

The population of this territory has long been engaged in the production of cotton and the manufacture of various fabrics from it. For spinning fabrics at home, the cotton seeds were separated using a special device "halaji" Cotton and wool threads were spinning on a spinning wheel. Various fabrics were made from spinning threads on weaving devices, the so-called "dukans". Long elongated strands of fabric, spun on spinning machines, were called "tanda (stretched base) or "urish" (warp), and across stretched threads "ducks". The "tanda" (base) was passed through the shuttle and each time closed with the handle of the dukan". The fabric was measured in spans. The width of the fabric was short, that is, 35-40 cm. The material obtained twice from the weaving device "dukan" was enough for only one dress.

Baysun district was a center for spinning such materials as alacha, ganda, silk, Alacha is a striped fabric with red, crimson, blue and dark green lines. The material "ganda" was woven in the settlements of Saryasia, Baysun district. The famous spinner of the "Zhanda" was Muslim Kakhkharov, Cotton was brought from Dzharkurgan for spinning the "Zhanda," and paints from Denau. The width

of the Zhanda is 50 cm, for the manufacture of one cotton robe from it 7-8 meters of fabric were spent.

Sushi is a thin fabric with colored stripes. When spinning, the distance between the tanda and arkok threads was left free, and compared to the alaca, the sushi fabric was woven thinner and larger. One of the common fabrics that the villagers used to sew clothes was considered to be "buz" coarse cotton fabric of handicraft production. Buz, woven from cotton thread, had a rough look. Cocoons were processed to obtain silk, and silk threads were hidden on a spinning wheel. In addition, a rim, a braid sewn to the edges of a turban, as well as jewelry braided to braids, were made of cotton thread and fabric, thick cotton or silk threads of black color with metal balls and fringe at the ends.

The Baisun Atlas was very popular. Fabrics made by local artisans were dyed at home. The preparation of paints, the product of many years of experience and hard work, has been kept a secret for a long time, Local dyers used the peels and peel of such local plants as madder, mimosa to select colors for the paints. The process of dyeing the fabric was carried out before spinning. In addition, the fabric was given a printed pattern. When printing patterns on fabrics, several forms were used. A pattern was cut out on the front of the form, on which there was a main and an external line. Forms for engraving were prepared from the trunks of poplar, willow, maple, apricot (apricot), almond and walnut. A custard mixture was prepared from the stem, roots of dried plants and the crust of pomegranates, then it was mixed with thick glue of fruit tree with mixed aqueous iron rust, after which a black mixture was obtained. The forms immersed in black color were pressed (pressed) onto the fabric. Fabric dyers called "nilchi", and flower pressers on matter called "chitgars" (rappers). The peculiar style of each master was clearly manifested in the process when filling the pattern on the fabric. Flower forms were strong, inherited from father to son. The nomadic and semi-nomadic population spun wool fabric. At first, the wool was washed well and disheveled with a wool comb, then with a special bunch of rods the wool was frayed, spun and brought to the state of a thread. Woolen threads were boiled in salt water. Therefore, woolen threads were durable and wearable. The breeders who lived in the steppe, mountain and foothill areas from wool, in addition to clothing, prepared household items: carpets, bags, felt, baggage bags and napramachi (a folding bag made of durable fabric).

Sheep, camel hair and goat fluff were considered the main raw material in the manufacture of fabric. Downy shawls, turbaned and footcloths were made from

goat hair, From camel hair, mainly sewn chekmen. The aristocrats of the Kungirat and Datura tribe had outer clothing made of white checkmen. In addition, zhaynamaz-a prayer rug, tablecloths, and even kurpachi-woolen blankets were made from camel hair. On handicraft weaving devices, that is, ummacs, a "shol"-woolen fabric was made from yarn made from sheep's wool. In a word, weaving, is an integral part of the craft, plays an important role in the life of the population, having a serious impact on the culture of dressing.

References:

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